

Volumetric and viscometric studies of mono- and disaccharides in water and in mixed solvent (formamide + water) systems at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K

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Abstract : Apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) and viscosities (η) of solutions of mono- and disaccharides viz. glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose have been determined in water and in [formamide (FA) + water] mixed solvent systems of varying compositions (10, 20 and 30%, v/v) at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K as a function of molar concentration. The V_ϕ and η data have been analysed in the light of Masson and Jones-Dole equations respectively. The activation thermodynamic quantities ($\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$, $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta S_2^{0\#}$) of viscous flow for mono- and disaccharides in water and in (formamide + water) mixed solvent systems have been determined at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K. The results in regard to solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions in water and (formamide + water) mixed solvent systems have been discussed in terms of the values of constants of Masson and Jones-Dole equations. The results of the study reveal that mono- and disaccharides behave as structure makers in water and also in (formamide + water) mixed solvent systems.

Keywords : Molar volume, viscosity, mixed solvents, disaccharides.

Banipal and co-workers¹ have carried out studies relating to the measurement of partial molar volumes of some saccharides in water and in aqueous solutions of urea, guanidine hydrochloride, sodium chloride, cupric chloride and in zinc chloride. Partial molar volume data have been used to calculate partial molar volumes of transfer ($V_{2,tr}^0$) for various saccharides from water to aqueous urea/sodium chloride/zinc chloride/guanidine hydrochloride/cupric chloride solutions. The values of $V_{2,tr}^0$ have been rationalized in terms of solute-co-solute interactions.

Viscosities of mannose, fructose, sucrose and maltose in water and in (water + acetonitrile) and (water + dimethyl sulphoxide) mixed solvents at different temperatures have been reported². The results of the study have been discussed on the basis of the values of coefficients A and B of Jones-Dole equation.

It appears that studies relating to determination of apparent molar volumes and viscosities of solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in formamide (FA) + water mixed solvent systems vis-à-vis solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions are still lacking. Hence, the title study has been undertaken in the light of the following aspects : (i) Determinations of apparent molar volume (V_ϕ) from density data as a function of molar

concentration of solutions of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose in water and also in formamide (FA) + water mixed solvent systems of varying composition (10, 20 and 30%, v/v) at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K; (ii) Determination of limiting apparent molar volume (V_ϕ^0) of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose in purely aqueous solutions as well as in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures; (iii) Determination of partial molar volumes of transfer ($V_{2,tr}^0$) of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose from water to (FA + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures; (iv) Determination of viscosities of solutions of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose in water and in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures, and subsequent analysis of viscosity-concentration data in the light of Jones-Dole equation; and (v) Determination of free energies of activation of viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_1^0$ and $\Delta\mu_2^0$ per mole of solvent and solute respectively, at different temperatures and subsequent calculation of entropy ($\Delta S_2^{0\#}$) and enthalpy ($\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) of activation of viscous flow at different temperatures.

Results and discussion

The apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of mono- and

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disaccharides in water and in (FA + water) and mixed solvent systems of varying compositions viz. 10, 20 and 30% (v/v) formamide (FA) as a function of molar concentration (C) of the solutes have been determined at different temperatures viz. 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K using the following equation

$$V_{\phi} = \frac{1000}{C\rho_0} (\rho_0 - \rho) + \frac{M}{\rho_0} \quad (1)$$

where *M* is the molecular weight of the solute, and ρ_0 and ρ are the densities of solvent and solution respectively.

The apparent molar volumes (V_{ϕ}) and densities of the solutions of a typical saccharide (fructose) as a function of *C* are presented in Table 1.

The plots of V_{ϕ} versus \sqrt{C} are linear in each case in accordance with Masson's equation

$$V_{\phi} = V_{\phi}^0 + S_v \sqrt{C} \quad (2)$$

where V_{ϕ}^0 is the limiting apparent molar volume of the solute and is equal to the partial molar volume at infinite dilution (V_{ϕ}^0), and S_v is the experimental slope. The $V_{\phi} -$

Table 1. Densities and apparent molar volumes of solutions of fructose in water and in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition at different temperatures

Concentration (C) of fructose (mol dm ⁻³)	ρ (g cm ⁻³)			V_{ϕ} (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
	Solvent : Water					
0.0	0.9982	0.9957	0.9922	-	-	-
0.2	1.0153	1.0727	1.0092	94.94	95.41	96.07
0.4	1.0326	1.0299	1.0264	94.30	95.00	95.50
0.6	1.0511	1.0485	1.0447	92.10	92.40	93.50
0.8	1.0713	1.0678	1.0649	88.90	90.40	90.00
1.0	1.0918	1.0891	1.0861	86.70	87.10	87.00
1.2	1.1138	1.1102	1.1086	84.00	85.10	83.80
1.4	1.1368	1.1347	1.1298	81.30	81.20	82.50
1.6	1.1595	1.1589	1.1557	79.50	78.50	78.60
1.8	1.1845	1.1808	1.1803	76.80	76.00	77.90
2.0	1.2088	1.2062	1.2017	75.00	75.20	76.00
	Solvent : 10% FA + Water					
0.0	1.0053	1.0012	0.997	-	-	-
0.2	1.0151	1.0123	1.0087	95.99	97.10	98.70
1.0	1.0919	1.0901	1.0855	86.60	86.10	87.60
1.6	1.1606	1.1589	1.1535	87.80	78.50	80.00
2.0	1.2115	1.2092	1.2047	73.66	73.70	74.48
	Solvent : 20% FA + Water					
0.0	1.0112	1.0091	1.0038	-	-	-
0.2	1.0148	1.012	1.0086	97.51	98.72	99.13
1.0	1.0936	1.0892	1.1086	84.90	87.00	87.10
1.6	1.1587	1.1598	1.1559	80.00	77.90	78.50
2.0	1.2130	1.2098	1.2064	72.90	73.42	73.63
	Solvent : 30% FA + Water					
0.0	1.0143	1.0116	1.0082	-	-	-
0.2	1.0147	1.0120	1.0084	97.68	98.72	99.81
1.0	1.0928	1.0892	1.0866	85.70	87.00	86.50
1.6	1.1614	1.1589	1.1565	78.30	78.50	78.10
2.0	1.2162	1.2113	1.2081	71.30	72.65	72.78

C data have been fitted to the Masson's equation and values of constants V_{ϕ}^0 and S_v have been obtained by the method of least squares. The results are presented in Table 2. It is seen that the values of V_{ϕ}^0 are largely positive in water as well as in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures, which indicate³ the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions. Further, on comparing the values of V_{ϕ}^0 in pure water with those in presence of (FA + water) mixed solvent systems, it is found that there occurs an increase in V_{ϕ}^0 with the increasing amount of formamide in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems thereby indicating an increase in the strength of solute-solvent interactions. On the other hand, the values of S_v are negative in water and are further rendered increasingly more negative with the increase in formamide content in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems. This suggests the presence of weak solute-solute interactions which are further weakened with the increase in the content of formamide in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems. Thus, on the basis of the values of V_{ϕ}^0 and S_v for mono- and disaccharides in pure water and those obtained in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems, it may be concluded that the molecules of mono- and disaccharides become more solvated in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems as compared to in pure water resulting in increased solute-solvent interactions and decreased solute-solute interactions. A perusal of Table 2 also shows that with rise of temperature from 293.15 to 313.15 K the values of V_{ϕ}^0 tend to increase while those of S_v tend to decrease.

From the it follows that solute-solvent interactions tend to become stronger with the rise of temperature, while the reverse is true for solute-solute interactions.

Partial molar volumes of transfer ($V_{2,tr}^0$) for glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose from water to (FA + water) mixed solvent systems have been obtained as below :

$$V_{2,tr}^0 = V_2^0(\text{FA + water}) - V_2^0(\text{water}) \quad (3)$$

It is found that in each case the values of $V_{2,tr}^0$ are positive and tend to become more positive with the increasing content of formamide in (formamide + water) mixed solvent systems. The positive values of $V_{2,tr}^0$ may be explained in the light of different models⁴. Partial molar volume, V_2^0 of a non-electrolyte at infinite dilution is a combination of the intrinsic volume (V_{int}) of the non-electrolyte and volume due to its interaction with solvent (V_s) which was further modified later as⁴ :

$$V_2^0 = V_{v,w} + V_{void} - V_{shrinkage} \quad (4)$$

where $V_{v,w}$ is the Van der Waals volume, V_{void} is the associated void or empty volume and $V_{shrinkage}$ is volume of shrinkage⁵. It has been assumed that $V_{v,w}$ and V_{void} have the same magnitude in water and in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems. Therefore, the positive $V_{2,tr}^0$ values from water to (FA + water) mixed solvent systems can be attributed to the decrease in the volume of shrinkage because of stronger interactions between formamide and hydroxyl groups (-OH) of saccharides. Furthermore, these

Table 2. Values of limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}^0) and experimental slope (S_v) for solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition at different temperatures

Mono- and disaccharides	V_{ϕ}^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)				S_v (cm ³ dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-3/2})			
	Water	10% FA	20% FA	30% FA	Water	10% FA	20% FA	30% FA
Temperature 293.15 K								
Glucose	112.34	114.74	116.06	118.61	-26.54	-28.03	-30.15	-32.55
Fructose	111.39	113.92	115.78	117.28	-25.40	-27.79	-29.82	-31.68
Sucrose	212.04	214.93	216.42	218.76	-47.12	-49.31	-51.12	53.84
Maltose	228.61	230.49	232.06	231.19	-56.72	-58.28	-60.93	-62.60
Temperature 303.15 K								
Glucose	113.37	115.09	117.18	119.61	-27.85	-29.71	-31.05	-33.01
Fructose	112.78	114.95	116.94	118.82	-26.27	-28.80	-30.61	-32.97
Sucrose	213.68	215.74	217.05	219.87	-48.76	-50.37	-52.23	-54.54
Maltose	229.88	231.69	233.61	235.77	-57.44	-59.75	-61.30	-63.56
Temperature 313.15 K								
Glucose	114.41	116.52	118.52	120.91	-28.94	-30.31	-32.06	34.40
Fructose	113.89	115.68	117.85	119.88	-27.30	-29.32	-31.04	-33.16
Sucrose	214.96	216.94	218.46	220.55	-49.33	-51.40	-53.14	-55.10
Maltose	230.82	232.91	234.45	236.99	-58.16	-60.75	62.65	-64.67

interactions will reduce the structure breaking effect of formamide on water. In other words, more water is released as bulk water in the presence of saccharides. Since bulk water has higher volume contribution than structure-broken water, therefore this factor will also contribute to positive value of $V_{2,tr}^0$ observed in the present study.

Viscosities of solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems have been determined at different temperatures as a function of molar concentration of the solute solutions. The representative data (for fructose) are presented in Table 3. The viscosity data have been analysed in the light of Jones-Dole equation

$$\eta/\eta_0 = \eta_{rel} = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (5)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{(\eta_{rel} - 1)}{\sqrt{C}} = A + B\sqrt{C} \quad (6)$$

It is found that the plots of $(\eta_{rel} - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ versus \sqrt{C} are linear in each case. The values of coefficients A and B

Table-3 (contd.)

0.2	0.9842	0.8012	0.7432
1.0	1.6154	1.2438	1.0057
1.2	1.8327	1.4037	1.1380
1.8	2.4006	1.9214	1.7837
2.0	2.6592	2.1063	1.9742
Solvent : 30% FA + Water			
0.0	0.9898	0.8614	0.7708
0.2	0.8641	0.8641	0.7742
1.0	1.5792	1.2229	1.1823
1.6	2.2167	1.7865	1.6786
2.0	2.6662	2.2131	2.9159

have been determined by the method of least squares and the values are presented in Table 4. It is seen that the values of A are negative in water as well as in (FA + water) mixed solvents systems which indicate the presence of weak solute-solute interactions. On the other hand, the values of coefficient B are positive which suggest the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions in the solutions of mono- and disaccharides. Further, the values of B are rendered more positive in the presence of (FA + water) mixed solvent systems as compared to those in pure water. This may be ascribed to the increased solute-solvent interactions in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems. Further, the positive values of B for mono- and disaccharides in water and in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems indicate⁶ that mono- and disaccharides behave as structure makers in these solvents.

Free energies of activation of viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ per mole of solvent and solute respectively were calculated as below :

The coefficient B of the Jones-Dole equation is related to the free energy of activation by the following equation⁷ :

$$B = \frac{\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0}{1000} + \frac{\bar{V}_1^0}{1000} [(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#})/RT] \quad (7)$$

where \bar{V}_1^0 and \bar{V}_2^0 are the partial molar volumes of the solvent and solute respectively, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ is the free energy of activation per mole of solvent and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ is the free energy of activation per mole of solute. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and therefore those $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ were calculated using the following equations.

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#} = RT \ln \left[\frac{\eta_0 V_1^0}{hN} \right] \quad (8)$$

Table 3. Viscosities of solutions of fructose in water and in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition at different temperatures

Concentration (C) of fructose (mol dm ⁻³)	η (m Pa.s)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
Solvent : Water			
0.0	1.0020	0.7977	0.6532
0.2	1.0396	0.8957	0.6658
0.4	1.1414	0.8885	0.7207
0.6	1.2186	0.9805	0.8467
0.8	1.3975	1.1259	0.9412
1.0	1.5215	1.2763	1.0802
1.2	1.7469	1.4269	1.2561
1.4	1.8940	1.5905	1.3651
1.6	2.2154	1.7260	1.5224
1.8	2.4016	1.9047	1.6163
2.0	2.5908	2.1063	1.7450
Solvent : 10% FA + Water			
0.0	0.9119	0.7079	0.5899
0.2	1.0357	0.8876	0.6551
1.0	1.5561	1.2763	1.0629
1.6	2.2096	1.8017	1.4959
2.0	2.5872	2.1966	1.7425
Solvent : 20% FA + Water			
0.0	0.9246	0.7970	0.7349

Table 4. Values of coefficients *A* and *B* of Jones-Dole equation for solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition at different temperatures

Mono- and disaccharides	<i>A</i> (dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-1/2})				<i>B</i> (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)			
	Water	10% FA	20% FA	30% FA	Water	10% FA	20% FA	30% FA
Temperature 293.15 K								
Glucose	-0.682	-0.714	-0.957	-0.982	1.272	1.291	1.430	1.554
Fructose	-0.641	-0.688	-0.802	-0.880	1.227	1.273	1.395	1.448
Sucrose	-1.232	-1.237	-1.504	-1.689	3.747	3.751	4.027	4.129
Maltose	-1.350	-1.930	-2.036	-2.912	3.850	4.079	4.172	4.218
Temperature 303.15 K								
Glucose	-0.704	-0.738	-0.974	-0.989	1.311	1.540	1.507	1.621
Fructose	-0.656	-0.704	-0.876	-0.907	1.262	1.330	1.432	1.478
Sucrose	-1.251	-1.310	-1.603	-1.788	3.817	3.865	4.105	4.253
Maltose	-1.357	-1.993	-2.224	-2.325	3.901	4.202	4.278	4.398
Temperature 313.15 K								
Glucose	-0.713	-0.952	-0.982	-0.996	1.377	1.581	1.851	1.931
Fructose	-0.663	-0.823	-0.883	-0.912	1.328	1.443	1.530	1.778
Sucrose	-1.279	-1.403	-1.641	-1.847	3.882	3.988	4.208	4.380
Maltose	-1.377	-2.148	-2.339	-2.486	3.996	4.349	4.408	4.497

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_1^{0\#} + \frac{RT}{\bar{V}_1^0} [1000 B - (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)] \quad (9)$$

where *R*, *h* and *N* are gas constant, Planck constant and Avogadro's number respectively; and *T* is the absolute temperature.

The entropy of activation ($\Delta S_2^{0\#}$) of viscous flow for mono- and disaccharides has been calculated from the following relation⁷

$$\frac{d(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#})}{dT} = -\Delta S_2^{0\#} \quad (10)$$

The enthalpy of activation ($\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) of viscous flow has been calculated with the help of the following equations⁸.

$$\Delta H_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_2^{0\#} + T\Delta S_2^{0\#} \quad (11)$$

The free energies of activation of viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, per mole of solvent and solute, respectively have been obtained as per the above mentioned procedure. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ have been presented in Table 5. It is seen that the values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ for mono- and disaccharides in water and also in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems are larger as compared to those of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and that in each case ($\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$) > 0. This shows that mono- and disaccharides behave as structure makers in water as well as in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems. The values of entropy and enthalpy of activation of viscous flow at different temperatures have been calculated and

Tables 5. Values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ for water and (FA + water) mixed solvent systems and those of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ for mono- and disaccharides in water and (FA + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures

	$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
Water	9.32	9.07	8.86
10% FA + water	9.15	9.22	8.28
20% FA + water	9.30	9.27	9.05
30% FA + water	9.84	9.84	9.74
$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)			
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
Glucose			
Water	193.88	205.02	220.12
10% FA + water	185.50	223.98	235.15
20% FA + water	189.72	205.12	254.11
30% FA + water	191.41	205.23	251.98
Fructose			
Water	187.70	198.08	213.12
10% FA + water	183.24	196.70	216.53
20% FA + water	188.72	199.10	217.09
30% FA + water	183.11	199.10	233.56
Sucrose			
Water	541.69	568.14	593.96
10% FA + water	513.95	543.88	576.04
20% FA + water	517.52	543.40	571.84
30% FA + water	495.73	525.41	556.01

Table-5 (contd.)

	Maltose		
Water	557.93	557.93	557.93
10% FA + water	557.93	592.99	627.11
20% FA + water	536.90	566.86	599.39
30% FA + water	507.44	544.02	571.95

analytical reagents grade of 99.9% purity and were used as such. The reagents were always placed in a desiccator over P₂O₅ to keep them in dry atmosphere.

Freshly doubly distilled water (sp. cond. $\sim 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) was used for preparing the solutions of mono- and disaccharides in purely aqueous medium as well in

Table 6. Entropy of activation and enthalpy of activation of viscous flow for solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition at different temperatures

Solvents	$T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)			$\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
Glucose						
Water	97.36	102.37	109.24	291.24	148.4	158.99
10% FA + water	-727.78	-752.6	-777.43	-542.28	-528.62	-542.28
20% FA + water	-943.71	-975.91	-1008.1	-753.99	-770.79	-753.99
30% FA + water	-887.9	-918.19	-948.48	-696.50	-712.96	-696.50
Fructose						
Water	90.74	95.41	101.81	278.44	141.43	151.56
10% FA + water	-487.93	-504.58	-521.22	-304.7	-307.88	-304.7
20% FA + water	-415.76	-429.94	1444.12	-227.03	-230.84	-227.03
30% FA + water	-739.35	-764.57	-789.79	-556.24	-572.44	-556.24
Sucrose						
Water	231.14	243.03	259.33	772.83	289.05	309.08
10% FA + water	-910.07	-941.12	-972.16	-396.12	-397.24	-396.12
20% FA + water	-796.13	-823.28	-850.44	-278.61	-279.88	-278.61
30% FA + water	-883.58	-913.72	-943.86	-387.85	-388.32	-387.85
Maltose						
Water	212.25	223.17	238.14	770.18	269.20	287.89
10% FA + water	-1013.97	-1048.56	-1083.15	-456.04	-455.57	-456.04
20% FA + water	-915.98	-947.23	-978.48	-379.09	-380.37	-379.09
30% FA + water	-945.51	-977.77	-1010.02	-438.07	-433.74	-438.07

presented in Table 6. It is seen that the values of both $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ are positive in water but are negative in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems of varying compositions. From this it follows that in purely aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides the transition state is associated with bond-breaking and a decrease in order. This suggests that the slip-plane is some where in the region of centro-symmetric order⁷. On the other hand, the negative values $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ for solutions of mono- and disaccharides in (FA + water) mixed solvent systems show that the formation of the transition-state is associated with bond-making and an increase in order. This suggests that slip-plane is in the disordered region.

Experimental

Glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose were of

formamide (FA) + water mixed solvent systems of varying compositions (10, 20 and 30%, v/v). An electronic balance having an accuracy of 1.0×10^{-4} g was used for the mass measurements.

Densities of solvents and solutions were measured as described earlier⁹. The uncertainty of the density measurements was estimated to be less than 1×10^{-4} g cm⁻³. Viscosities of the solvents and solutions were measured at the desired temperature using an Ostwald's suspended level type viscometer as per details given by Findlay¹⁰. The uncertainty of calculated absolute viscosities was $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ m Pa.s. Density and viscosity measurements were carried out in a thermostatic bath, the temperature of which was maintained to within ± 0.01 K of the desired value.

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